

Accessibility Self-Assessment for Recreational Programs

Type of Accessibility	Description
Financial	<i>Cost of attending programs</i> , including membership fees, registration fees, equipment and child-care in relation to income/budget
Geographic	<i>Travel time and travel cost</i> . Travel time includes walk, wait and in-vehicle time in relation to available time budget. Travel cost includes public transit or vehicle expenses (gas, parking) in relation to travel budget. Travel time can be calculated from home, school and/or work, depending on the communities served. In some cases, travel time can be reduced by locating services close to hubs such as shopping centres or one-stop service centres so that the costs of travel can be divided among other activities. Community accessibility for schools and health care is often described in terms of distance or time thresholds (standard thresholds are 20 minutes' walk to a school or 30 minutes' travel time to a health care provider).
Temporal	<i>Timing of program and support services</i> (e.g., drop-in child-care or parallel programming for family members) in relation to available schedule. The schedule should be convenient for the targeted users. Programs should not disrupt schooling or work schedules and should permit people with limited incomes to participate. Schedules may need to be coordinated with local schools and agencies.
Physical	<i>Availability of ramps and curb cuts for physical locations</i> , including ingress from the parking lot or WheelTrans drop-off, and including washrooms, based on barrier-free guidelines (must be associated with programming that meets needs of people with mobility impairments)
Informational	<i>Availability and usability of information</i> regarding services; updated schedules on web, correct schedules posted in local schools, social service agencies, government services, immigrant service agencies. Includes outreach, plain language, different languages, as well as referral links to and from other services. Also includes appropriate placement of triggers ('hot triggers' occur at the right time and place for immediate action).
Cultural and Sub-cultural	<i>Relevance of programs to user groups</i> , including gender, age, ethno-cultural background, social class and group identity. Every activity carries social markers that attract some groups and repel others – think shuffleboard, cricket, ping pong and football. Perceived safety and security can be a part of this element, as can locations that minimize stigma. This type of accessibility can be achieved by involving the users in developing new programs and services and improving existing ones, as well as identifying barriers.
Specific Accommodations	Many individuals need <i>specific accommodations</i> , which may include sign language interpreting, visual aids, help in explaining complicated instructions, and so on. These must be provided on an individual basis unless your agency is reaching out to those groups, or serves a community with a large number of people with those characteristics.

Self-Assessment Tool

Type of Accessibility	Description	Self-Assessment Questions	Possible Activities
Financial	<i>Cost of attending programs</i> , including membership fees, registration fees, sports equipment and child-care in relation to income/budget	<p>What is the financial profile of your community? E.g., how many households/children/youth are living on low incomes?</p> <p>Do you offer low cost programs, including sports equipment and travel expectations, that are affordable within the budget of your local community?</p>	<p>Define feasible health and recreation budgets for low income individuals and families in your community. (For example, in community X 20% of the families have a household income of \$26,000 or lower. A breakdown of Statistics Canada's Market Basket Measure¹ in that region suggests that an appropriate family budget for recreational services would be under \$20/month.) Develop a strategy that ensures that vulnerable children and youth have access to the programs that will have the most impact on health (e.g., subsidized individual memberships at a price they can afford, vs low-cost specific programming to groups)</p>
Geographic	<i>Travel time and travel cost</i> . Travel time includes walk, wait and in-vehicle time in relation to available time budget. Travel cost includes public transit or vehicle expenses (gas, parking) in relation to travel budget. Travel time can be calculated from home, school and/or work, depending on the communities served. In some cases, travel time can be reduced by locating services close to hubs such as shopping centres or one-stop service centres so that the costs of travel can be divided among other activities. Community accessibility for schools and health care is often described in terms of distance or time thresholds (standard thresholds are 20 minutes' walk to a school or 30 minutes' travel time to a health care	<p>Where are the low income and vulnerable people in your community?</p> <p>How many minutes would it take them to walk to appropriate programs from their homes, schools, workplaces?</p> <p>How much would it cost them per month to travel to appropriate programs?</p>	<p>Develop income maps of your community to find out if you are providing programs close to your target populations.</p> <p>Open branch facilities near target populations, or partner with other facilities (eg, schools and malls) to get closer to your priority communities.</p>

¹ 'Membership fees for sports and recreation facilities' and 'single use fees for sports and recreation facilities' are two of the categories in Statistics Canada's Market Basket Measure for low income families. They exclude costs for most recreational equipment. For details see <http://www.statcan.ca/english/research/75F0002MIE/75F0002MIE2004001.pdf>, <http://www.hrsdc.gc.ca/en/cs/sp/sdc/pkrf/publications/research/2002-000662/SP-628-05-06e.pdf>, http://www.cpra.ca/UserFiles/File/EN/sitePdfs/initiatives/Barriers_Report.pdf

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	provider).		
Temporal	<i>Timing of program and support services</i> (e.g., drop-in child-care or parallel programming for family members) in relation to available schedule. The schedule should be convenient for the targeted users. Programs should not disrupt schooling or work schedules and should permit people with limited incomes to participate. Schedules may need to be coordinated with local schools and agencies.	Is there a match between the times that the service is available and the times that people are able or willing to access them? (i.e., is it reasonable to get there in time given public transit schedules after work?)	Get input from your target populations through interviews and focus groups at their locations and at times convenient for them.
Physical	<i>Availability of ramps and curb cuts throughout the facility</i> , including ingress from the parking lot or cab stand, and including washrooms, based on barrier-free guidelines (must be associated with programming that meets needs of people with mobility impairments)	Have you had an accessibility audit by someone familiar with provincial requirements (e.g., the Ontarians with Disabilities Act?)(As an example) Can someone in a wheelchair comfortably and independently access your buildings from the outside? (Check from the external sidewalk or parking lot right through to the dressing rooms and pool.)	Obtain an accessibility audit from an expert or do a self-assessment using an updated checklist (possibly from a local organization that has done a good accessibility plan)
Informational	<i>Availability and usability of information</i> regarding program options; updated schedules on web, correct schedules posted in local schools, social service agencies, government services, immigrant service agencies. Includes outreach, plain language, different languages, as well as referral links to and from other services.	Are your schedules posted in locations that are frequented by your target population? Are they updated and accurate? Are they readable (in appropriate language or literacy level)? Do other organizations know about your services, and do they refer participants to them?	Get community demographic profile and identify the languages and educational levels of your community. Post updated schedules in appropriate languages and do outreach with organizations and schools
Cultural and Sub-cultural	<i>Relevance of programs to various groups in your catchment area</i> , including gender, age, ethno-cultural background, social class and group identity. Shuffleboard, skipping-rope, cricket, basketball all make statements about who you are serving. Services for 6 year old Mennonite girls look different from services for First Nations teenaged boys,	Are the services appropriate for your target population(s)? Do you offer activities to vulnerable children, youth and families in your community? Are there special needs for girls? New immigrants? Working mothers?	Get input from your target populations through interviews and focus groups at their locations and at times convenient for them.

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	<p>or for elderly Italian men. Perceived safety and security can be a part of this element, as can locations that minimize stigma. This type of accessibility can be achieved by involving the users in developing new programs and services and improving existing ones, as well as identifying barriers.</p>		
<p>Specific Accommodations</p>	<p>Many individuals need <i>specific accommodations</i>, which may include sign language interpreting, visual aids, help in explaining complicated instructions, and so on. These must be provided on an individual basis unless your agency is reaching out to those groups, or serves a community with a large number of people with those characteristics.</p>	<p>Does your agency know where to find appropriate accommodations (e.g, sign language interpreters)?</p> <p>Is there a budget for accommodations?</p>	<p>Provide a convenient way for participants to request help (e.g., at reception), and ensure that someone is assigned to follow up on these requests.</p>